

The Optimal Geometries of Piezoelectric Effect in Trigonal Crystals

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Piezoelectric materials have traditionally attracted considerable attention due to their ability to convert mechanical energy into electrical one and vice versa. This property makes them suitable for a variety of applications such as sensors, actuators, transducers, generators of acoustic waves etc. As it follows from the theoretical analysis of the piezoelectric effect, its magnitude depends significantly on the character of the applied mechanical stress field. At that an important parameter that characterizes the energy efficiency of piezoelectric device is the electromechanical coupling coefficient (ECC) which is a numerical measure of the conversion efficiency between electrical and mechanical energy. The ECC is determined as the square root of the ratio of electrical energy to the sum of electrical and elastic ones, and can be calculated in accordance with the expression

$$K = \frac{E_i d_{ijk} \sigma_{jk}}{\sqrt{(E_i \varepsilon_{ij} E_j) (\sigma_{ij} s_{ijkl} \sigma_{kl})}}, \quad (1)$$

where E_i are the components of electrical field intensity, σ_{jk} are the components of mechanical stress, d_{ijk} are piezoelectric coefficients, ε_{ij} are the dielectric permittivities, s_{ijkl} are the elastic compliance coefficients, over repeating indices the summation is carried out in (1).

To ensure the the highest possible value of the ECC, the optimal cut of piezoelectric crystal should be determined. As it is followed from (1), the ECC depends on the direction of the electrical field and the the relationship between the components of the mechanical stress tensor, but not on the absolute values of the electrical intensity or the mechanical stress. Thus, the determination of the optimal geometry of piezoelectric effect can be carried out in the same way as for the cases of optically induced or non-linear optical effects, i.e. by construction and analysis of the extreme surfaces representing the possible maxima of piezoelectric effect for all possible directions of electrical field. Here such a problem is considered for trigonal crystals belonging to point groups of symmetry 3m and 32 - lithium niobate and tantalate (3m), langasite and quartz (32).

The problem is analyzed in two formulations: (i) the uniaxial pressure is applied; (ii) the mechanical stress field has got the arbitrary character, i.e. six independent components σ_{jk} are considered as the parameters of optimization (the general case). As it is shown, in the case of uniaxial pressure the optimal geometry of the effect is significantly different from orthogonal one for crystals of point group 3m (LiNbO₃, LiTaO₃), whereas for crystals of point group 32 (La₃Ga₅SiO₁₄, SiO₂), on the contrary, it is practically coincides with orthogonal, while the directions of electric tension and uniaxial compression are mutually perpendicular. The highest value of the EEC was found for the lithium niobate crystal, it is equal to 0.87, whereas for LiTaO₃ $K = 0.47$, for La₃Ga₅SiO₁₄ $K = 0.17$, for SiO₂ $K = 0.12$. In the general case, the highest achievable values of the EEC increase in comparison with the case of uniaxial pressure within units - tens of percent: 7% for LiNbO₃ (till 0.93), 33% for SiO₂ (till 0.16). The obtained results can be used to increase the efficiency of piezoelectric devices.

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